

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF PATHOLOGICAL NEOPLASMS OF THE ORAL CAVITY

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Abstract: A tooth cyst is a pathological neoplasm that occurs as a result of the body's protective reaction to infection or injury. A cyst occurs if pathogenic microorganisms that cause inflammation enter the jawbone through the root canal. Gradually, the cells involved in the painful process die, forming a cavity in the bone tissue. To prevent the spread of the process, our body forms a capsule with dense walls around the necrosis zone.

Keywords: retention cyst of the oral cavity, diagnostics, dentistry

Introduction. The resulting neoplasm contains inflammatory fluid, dead cells, decay products and bacteria. The sizes range from a few millimeters to several centimeters. Small (less than 5 mm in diameter) are called granulomas. Granuloma, cyst and cyst are the stages of the inflammatory process in the bone tissue of the jaw. As long as it is small, there will be no manifestations. The number of microbes in it continues to grow, but since this happens under the control of the immune system, the process develops imperceptibly. Immune cells are sent to the cyst through the blood vessels that feed the bone tissue. This is how the body tries to cope with the problem. But if the immune system weakens, the disease enters an acute phase.

The development of the disease can lead to serious consequences. An increase in size threatens with a fracture (especially of the lower jaw), loss of teeth involved in the inflammatory process, and degeneration into a malignant tumor. Exacerbation of the disease leads to the development of periostitis, purulent abscess or even osteomyelitis. If the patient does not receive qualified medical care at this stage, sepsis may begin. This is an extremely serious condition characterized by infection entering the bloodstream and its subsequent spread throughout the body.

Causes of occurrence

- untreated complicated caries;
- improper root canal treatment;
- injuries;
- irrational prosthetics leading to overloading of individual teeth;
- pathology of the development of the upper or lower jaw;
- infectious diseases of the oral cavity and nasopharynx.

Regardless of the causes of the cyst, treatment should be entrusted to dentists in order to prevent complications.

It is most often formed as a result of traumatic injury or infection, for example, with poor-quality filling of the root canal in the sinus of the tooth. Often this pathology occurs against the background of frequent sinusitis. Her treatment should begin with a visit to the dentist and an X-ray. At an early stage, it does not manifest itself in any way. The primary symptom is discomfort when chewing solid food.

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